

BEYOND ALL LIMITS CONGRESS 2018

International Congress on Sustainability in
Architecture, Planning, and Design

Proceedings Book of The Extended Abstracts

ÇANKAYA UNIVERSITY

Università
degli Studi
della Campania
Luigi Vanvitelli

UNIVERSITY OF
PLYMOUTH

October
17-18-19
Ankara, Turkey

Proceedings Book of Extended Abstracts

BEYOND ALL LIMITS / 2018

International Congress on Sustainability

in Architecture, Planning, and Design

ÇANKAYA UNIVERSITY
MAIN CAMPUS

October 17-18-19, 2018

ÇANKAYA UNIVERSITY

Università
degli Studi
della Campania
Luigi Vanvitelli

UNIVERSITY OF PLYMOUTH

Publishing Board: Rabia Çiğdem ÇAVDAR
Papatya Nur DÖKMECİ YÖRÜKOĞLU
Leyla ETYEMEZ ÇIPLAK
Timuçin HARPUTLUGİL
Zerrin Ezgi KAHRAMAN
Ezgi ORHAN
Ayça ÖZMEN
Şafak SAKÇAK
Özge SÜZER

Cover Design: Çetin TÜNGER
Printed in: October, 2018
Printed by: Teknoart Digital Ofset Reklamcılık Matbaacılık İth. İhr. San. ve Tic. Ltd. Şti.
Cevizlidere Mah. 1288 Sok. No:1/1
Çankaya | Ankara | Turkey
+90 312 473 92 97 | info@printandsmile.com.tr

ISBN: 978-975-6734-20-9

Copyright © 2018 by Çankaya University Press. All rights reserved. No part of this publication may be reproduced, stored in a retrieval system, or transmitted, in any form or by any means, electronic, mechanical, photocopying, recording or otherwise, except as permitted by Çankaya University.

In any case regarding the extended abstract/manuscript, the publisher/Çankaya University will not be responsible for handling any claims relating to authorship. The author(s) will have full responsibility for the contents of their extended abstract.

ÇANKAYA UNIVERSITY

Main Campus : Yukarıyurtçu Mahallesi Mimar Sinan Caddesi

No:4 06790, Etimesgut/ANKARA, +90 312 233 10 00

Balgat Campus: Çukurambar Mah. Öğretmenler Cad.

No: 14, 06530 Çankaya/ANKARA +90 312 284 45 00

<http://www.cankaya.edu.tr/>

Università
degli Studi
della Campania
Luigi Vanvitelli

Viale Abramo Lincoln n. 5, 81100 Caserta

P.IVA: 02044190615

protocollo@pec.unicampania.it

<https://www.unicampania.it/>

UNIVERSITY OF PLYMOUTH

Drake Circus, Plymouth

Devon PL4 8AA, United Kingdom

+44 1752 600600

<https://www.plymouth.ac.uk/>

COMMITTEES

Honorary Committee

Sıtkı ALP

Founder of Çankaya University

Dr. Hamdi MOLLAMAHMUTOĞLU, Prof.

Rector at Çankaya University

Dr. Giuseppe PAOLISSO, Prof.

Rector at Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”

Dr. Kenan TAŞ, Prof.

Vice Rector at Çankaya University

Dr. Hüseyin Selçuk GEÇİM, Prof.

Vice Rector at Çankaya University

Dr. G. Francesco NICOLETTI, Prof.

Vice Rector at Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”

Dr. Mario SPASIANO, Prof.

Vice Rector at Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”

Scientific Committee

Dr. Yasemin AFACAN, Assoc. Prof.	Bilkent University
Dr. Saadet AKBAY YENİGÜL, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Deniz ALTAY KAYA, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Stefano ANDREANI, Lecturer	Harvard University
Dr. Shady ATTIA, Prof.	University of Liège
Dr. Alessandro AURIGI, Prof.	University of Plymouth
Dr. Gülşah BAŞOK	Çankaya University
Dr. Mehmet Harun BATIRBAYGİL, Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Çiğdem BERDİ GÖKHAN, Assoc. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Lorenzo CAPOBIANCO, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Flaviano CELASCHI, Prof.	Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna
Dr. Chi Kwan CHAU, Assoc. Prof.	The Hong Kong Polytechnic University
Dr. Kalliopi CHOURMOUZIADOU, Lecturer	Hellenic Open University
Dr. Medardo CHIAPPONI, Prof.	Università IUAV di Venezia
Dr. Alessandra CIRAFICI, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Rabia Çiğdem ÇAVDAR	Çankaya University
Dr. Gülser ÇELEBİ, Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Arturo DELL’ACQUA BELLAVITIS, Prof.	Politecnico di Milano
Dr. Gianfranco DE MATTEIS, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Özgen Osman DEMİRBAŞ, Assoc. Prof.	İzmir University of Economics

Dr. Halime DEMİRKAN, Prof.	Bilkent University
Dr. Pınar DİNÇ KALAYCI, Prof.	Gazi University
Dr. Papatya Nur DÖKMECİ YÖRÜKOĞLU, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Hossam Eldin ELBOROMBOLY, Prof.	Ain Shams University
Dr. Cüneyt ELKER, Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Alpay ER, Prof.	Ozyegin University
Dr. Leyla ETYEMEZ ÇIPLAK	Çankaya University
Dr. Fabiana FORTE, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Rossella FRANCHINO, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Adriana GALDERISI, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Claudio GAMBARDELLA, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Claudio GERMAK, Prof.	Politecnico di Torino
Dr. Luigi GUERRIERO, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Arzuhan Burcu GÜLTEKİN, Assoc. Prof.	Ankara University
Dr. Timuçin HARPUTLUGİL, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Jan HENSEN, Prof.	Eindhoven University of Technology
Dr. Zerrin Ezgi KAHRAMAN, Assoc. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Jian KANG, Prof.	University College London
Dr. Ceren KATIPOĞLU, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Kıvanç KİTAPÇI	Çankaya University
Dr. Gül KOÇLAR URAL, Prof.	İstanbul Technical University
Dr. Satish Basavapatna KUMURA	University of Plymouth

Dr. Cüneyt KURTAY, Prof.	Gazi University
Dr. Shuli LIU, Prof.	Coventry University
Dr. Luigi MAFFEI, Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Elena MANZO, Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. İpek MEMİKOĞLU, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Francesca MUZZILLO, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Gülru MUTLU TUNCA, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Ezgi ORHAN, Asst. Prof	Çankaya University
Dr. Mustafa ÖNGE, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Zühal ÖZCAN, Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Simge ÖZDAL OKTAY	Çankaya University
Dr. Suna Senem ÖZDEMİR, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Ayça ÖZMEN	Çankaya University
Dr. Cengiz ÖZMEN, Assoc. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Fatma Gül ÖZTÜRK, Assoc. Prof	Çankaya University
Dr. Nicola PISACANE, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Daniela PISCITELLI, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Matthijs PRINS, Assoc. Prof.	Delft University of Technology
Dr. Patrizia RANZO, Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Ahmed RASHED, Prof.	British University in Egypt
Dr. Antonio ROSATO, Assoc. Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”

Dr. Silvana SEGAPPELI, Assoc. Prof.	Ecole Nationale Supérieure d'Architecture de Saint Etienne
Dr. Sergio SIBILIO, Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Dr. Ashish SHUKLA	Coventry University
Dr. Benedetta SPADOLINI, Prof.	Università degli Studi di Genova
Dr. Özge SÜZER, Asst. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Mehmet TUNÇER, Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Ali TÜREL, Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Gülsu ULUKAVAK HARPUTLUGİL, Assoc. Prof.	Çankaya University
Dr. Zeynep UYSAL ÜREY, Asst. Prof	Çankaya University
Dr. Shaonong WEI, Prof.	East China Normal University
Dr. Pieter de WILDE, Prof.	University of Plymouth
Dr. Ornella ZERLENGA, Prof.	Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”

Organizing Committee

Dr. Alessandro AURIGI, Prof.	Congress President
Dr. Mehmet Harun BATIRBAYGİL, Prof.	Congress President
Dr. Luigi MAFFEI, Prof.	Congress President
Dr. Claudio GAMBARDELLA, Assoc. Prof.	Congress Chair
Dr. Timuçin HARPUTLUGİL, Asst. Prof.	Congress Chair
Dr. Pieter de WILDE, Prof.	Congress Chair
Dr. Pasquale ARGENZIANO, Researcher	
Dr. Alessandra AVELLA, Researcher	
Dr. Francesca CASTANÒ, Assoc. Prof.	
Dr. Rabia Çiğdem ÇAVDAR	
Dr. Claudia CENNAMO, Researcher	
Dr. Gianluca CIOFFI, Contract Professor	
Dr. Ornella CIRILLO, Researcher	
Dr. Claudia DE BIASE, Resarcher	
Dr. Marina D'APRILE, Researcher	
Dr. Papatya Nur DÖKMECİ YÖRÜKOĞLU, Asst. Prof.	
Dr. Leyla ETYEMEZ ÇIPLAK	
Dr. Caterina FIORENTINO, Researcher	
Dr. Caterina FRETTOLOSO, Researcher	

Dr. Zerrin Ezgi KAHRAMAN, Assoc. Prof.

Dr. Ceren KATIPOĞLU, Asst. Prof.

Dr. Satish Basavapatna KUMURA

Dr. Massimiliano MASULLO, Assoc. Prof.

Dr. İpek MEMİKOĞLU, Asst. Prof.

Dr. Ezgi ORHAN, Asst. Prof.

Dr. Ayça ÖZMEN

Dr. Cengiz ÖZMEN, Assoc. Prof.

Dr. Fatma Gül ÖZTÜRK, Assoc. Prof.

Dr. Özge SÜZER, Asst. Prof.

Dr. Antonella VIOLANO, Assoc. Prof.

Çetin TÜNGER, Full Time Instr.

Webmaster

Elif AKSEL, Res. Asst.

Organizing Secretary

Feride Nazda GÜNGÖRDÜ, Res. Asst.

Organizing Secretary

FOREWORD

It is our great pleasure to welcome you to BEYOND ALL LIMITS 2018 - International Congress on Sustainability in Architecture, Planning, and Design, a joint collaboration of Çankaya University (Ankara-Turkey), Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli” (Caserta-Italy) and University of Plymouth (Plymouth-United Kingdom). The congress takes place in the Congress Hall of Çankaya University, Ankara, Turkey, on October 17-18-19, 2018 and supported by SID “Società Italiana Design”, SITdA “Società Italiana della Tecnologia dell'Architettura”, LeNS “The Learning Network on Sustainability” and GRID “Architecture, Planning and Design Journal”.

The congress aims to discuss and redefine the term sustainability with its all dimensions such as environmental, economic and sociocultural in various disciplines including architecture, planning and design, to extend the term’s boundaries through fulfilling it with scientific, genuine, innovative and inspiring studies and to foster cooperation within and between different disciplines at international level. Besides, workshops and special sessions are organized.

The scientific program consists of keynote speeches, plenary and parallel sessions of presentations and workshops. The 3-day congress has more than 200 contributing academicians, experts, researchers and professionals attending from several countries of the world. More than 100 presentations are planned in 28 sessions in 2 days. The third day is devoted to workshops which are organized by 8 different groups of academicians and professionals from related various fields. In addition to the contributed presentations and workshops, two invited keynote speeches are given: by Prof. Dr. Susan ROAF, Heriot Watt University’s Emeritus Professor of Architectural Engineering and Prof. Dr. Birol KILKIŞ, Başkent University’s Professor of Energy Engineering.

This proceedings book of extended abstracts comprises written contributions of the presentations, keynote speeches and workshops contents. Before the congress, all participants were expected to submit extended abstracts of their presentations in a format formed by a short abstract with keywords, introduction, methods, findings and discussion, conclusion and references, not exceeding 1500 words. All submitted extended abstracts were blind peer reviewed and accepted ones now take part in this book.

As being Congress Organization Committee, we would like to express our gratitude to all contributing members of Çankaya University, Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli” and the University of Plymouth for their superior efforts and enormous support. Furthermore, we would like to thank all participants of the congress for their outstanding contributions for sharing their knowledge, expertise and vision.

Congress Organization Committee

TABLE OF CONTENTS

COMMITTEES	1
Honorary Committee	1
Scientific Committee	2
Organizing Committee	6
FOREWORD	9
KEYNOTE SPEAKERS	21
How to Design a Comfortable Building <i>Susan Roaf</i>	22
'Sustainable' Systems and Equipment in Green Buildings-How Sustainable Are They? An Exergy Perspective <i>Birol Kılıç</i>	38
EXTENDED ABSTRACTS	41
The Use of Multi-Criteria Assessment Techniques in Defining Sustainable Transport Systems for Different Sized Cities Ankara and Rize Example <i>Furkan Akdemir, Hayri Ulvi, Aslınur Ekiz, Saim Yılmaz</i>	43
Courtyards thermal efficiency during hot regions' typical winter <i>Omar Al-Hafith, Satish B. K., Pieter de Wilde</i>	50
Resilience planning from theory to practice <i>Deniz Altay Kaya</i>	55
Why in-between spaces are important to everyday architecture? <i>Susana Alves</i>	59
Meaning in Cultural Sustainability <i>Gökçe Atakan, Saadet Akbay</i>	64
An Assessment of the Energy Performance Evaluation within the Form Conception Process <i>Cem Ataman, İpek Gürsel Dino</i>	70
The Computation of Performative Architecture within Integrated Design <i>Cem Ataman, İpek Gürsel Dino</i>	76
The Evaluation of Urban Mobility In Terms of Space and Equality, Case Study of Yozgat <i>İlker Atmaca, Seçil Gül Meydan Yıldız, Hazal Ilgın Bahçeci</i>	81
Remote sensing and sustainability. Case studies in Campania <i>Alessandra Avella, Pasquale Argenziano, Nicola Pisacane</i>	91

Bibliographic Evaluation of the Concept of Sustainability in the Postgraduate Theses of Architecture in Turkey <i>Özlem Aydın</i>	99
Analysis of Kızılcaşar Village in terms of Vernacular Architecture <i>Filiz Bal Koçyiğit, Nazlı Nazende Yıldırım, Papatya Nur Dökmeci Yörükoğlu</i>	105
Dimensions of War Destruction in the City of Benghazi <i>Abdelhamed Barani, Zerrin Ezgi Kahraman</i>	111
The Evaluation of Early Republican Industrial Buildings in Antalya in the Context of Cultural Sustainability <i>Emine Barbaros Akay, Yaren Şekerci, Hilal Tuğba Örmecioglu</i>	118
Evaluation of Sustainability of Housing Transformations in Copenhagen <i>Nezih Burak Bican</i>	123
Sustainability Beyond Architecture: Beyond Concepts, Beyond Scale and Beyond Time <i>Ebru Bingöl</i>	133
The Role of Participation in Identification and Sustainability of Heritage; the case of the Windmill of Heybeliada <i>Burcu Büken Cantimur, A. Binnur Kırış, Gülce G. Okyay</i>	137
Importance of the Sustainable Planning in Campus Settlement – A Negative Example: Aleaddin Keykubat Campus - Turkey <i>Süheyla Büyükaşahin Sıramkaya, Dicle Aydın, Esra Yaldız</i>	142
Sustainable methodologies for stability assessment of masonry vaulted structures <i>Daniela Cacace, Claudia Cennamo, Concetta Cusano, Gianfranco De Matteis</i>	148
Designed sustainability in Neapolitan Cultural Heritage. Some examples of argot design <i>Saverio Carillo, Pasquale Argenziano, Carolina Campone</i>	153
Libya, colonial architecture and tourist propaganda in the fascist rhetoric <i>Marco Carusone, Michela Russo, Roberta Bellucci</i>	161
Campania Felix from rural landscapes to smart lands <i>Francesca Castanò</i>	167
Adaptive reuse in sustainable development: the case study of Ercolano (Italy) <i>Francesca Ciampa, Martina Bosone</i>	174
Weaving the contemporary, Actuality in the use of raw materials in the production chain of the fashion industry <i>Elisabetta Cianfanelli, Renato Stasi, Margherita Tufarelli</i>	180
Towards an Idea of Countryside <i>Gianluca Cioffi</i>	184

Design as a critical interpretation of the world <i>Alessandra Cirafici, Fabrizia Ippolito, Caterina Fiorentino</i>	190
Social & cultural sustainability: Street Art In Italy <i>Vincenzo Cirillo</i>	195
Continuity and discontinuity in the drawing for the protection of religious heritage in the Balkans <i>Luigi Corniello, Andrea Maliqari, Carla Mottola, Enrico Mirra</i>	201
In terms of structure and expression. The possibilities of re-composition project <i>Francesco Costanzo</i>	207
Design research models for territories: local resources for social inclusion <i>Vincenzo Cristallo, Ivo Caruso</i>	215
Impacts of Recently Developed Squatter Settlements Transformation Projects on Urban Heat Islands: A Comparative Study in the City of Ankara <i>Ayşem Berrin, Funda Baş Bütüner</i>	220
An investigation on indoor soundscape in high school environment <i>Sıla Çankaya Topak</i>	226
From Badlands of Plastics to “Up-cycled” Objects: “Tertium Non Data” <i>Rabia Çiğdem Çavdar</i>	232
The Energy Effectiveness and Daylight Performance of Office Venetian Blinds <i>N. Mine Çelebi Yazıcıoğlu</i>	236
The Functional Continuity of Historic Cumhuriyet Square – Ayaş <i>Gülşah Çelik Başok</i>	247
Multiple Configurations of a Kinetic Shading System to Test Daylight Illuminance and Uniformity <i>Aslıhan Çevik Tuğçe Kazanasmaz</i>	253
Evaluating the Adaptation of Historic Buildings to New Functions in Terms of Sustainability: Afyonkarahisar Mihrioğlu Mansion <i>Gamze Çoban Pınar Dinç Kalaycı</i>	260
Sustainability and Built Heritage Conservation in today’s Italy: an appraisal between theory, method and practice <i>Marina D’Aprile</i>	269
The challenge of preserving heritage: A Neighbourhood case in Ardabil, Iran <i>Yousef Daneshvar Rouyandozagh, Ece Kumkale Acikgoz</i>	275
Urban Sustainable Innovative Actions: The I.Re.Ne. Project <i>Claudia De Biase, Michela Monaco, Maria Antonietta Sbordone</i>	282
The ecological and social role of open spaces in urban regeneration processes <i>Raffaella De Martino, Barbara di Vico</i>	287

Conservation state and structural deficiencies of typical Italian bridges <i>Gianfranco De Matteis, Mattia Zizi, Antonino Del Prete</i>	292
Influence of structural typologies on architectural style of high-rise steel buildings <i>Gianfranco De Matteis, Valentina Corlito, Graziella Soleti</i>	298
Beyond the limits of Building Performance Analysis <i>Pieter de Wilde</i>	306
Wind energy: differentiating perspectives <i>Başak Demir</i>	310
Adaptive Re-Use, Sustainability and the Modern Movement <i>Huriye Armağan Doğan</i>	315
Authenticity and Sustainability <i>Rui Duarte</i>	319
An Ecotourism-oriented Proposal in the Context of Sustainability: The Case of Rize Küşüve Village <i>Derya Elmalı Şen, Evşen Yetim, Elif Öztürk</i>	324
Effects of Architectural and Behavioural Factors on Indoor Air Quality in Residential Apartments <i>Ehab Ali Eshtiwi, Papatya Nur Dokmeci Yorukoglu</i>	331
Assessing the Sustainability of Historical Continuity in Multi-Layared Historic Towns: The Case of Amasya, Turkey <i>Leyla Etyemez Çıplak</i>	336
Room Impulse Response in Game Engines <i>Hasan Baran Fırat, Massimiliano Masullo, Luigi Maffei</i>	344
The influence of early Christian basilicas in the Byzantine East <i>Raffaella Fiorillo</i>	349
Large-scale ecosystems regeneration: enabling the transition to a circular economy in the Vesuvius coastal area <i>Rossella Franchino, Serena Viola</i>	356
BIM Technology and Material Innovation: From Efficiency to Environmental Compatibility <i>Rossella Franchino, Caterina Frettoloso, Nicola Pisacane</i>	362
Cities seek resilience: a network for a revalue urban identity <i>Caterina Frettoloso, Paola Gallo</i>	367
Energy Efficiencies of Cultural Heritage Through Recovery of Damages by Natural Event: The Case of The Gallery of Nations Inside the Church of Michelucci In Florence <i>Paola Gallo, Leonardo Boganini</i>	372
A museum system of design/craft for sustainable development in southern Italy <i>Claudio Gambardella, Dario Russo</i>	379

The Charterhouses in Campania: San Martino, a case to be reconsidered <i>María Fernanda, García Marino</i>	384
Sensory spatial appraisal of the Child Medical Unit of Mustapha Pacha hospital in Algiers <i>Nassila Ghida, K. Boussora</i>	390
Cultural Routes in South Italy: methods and projects <i>Anna Gianetti, Elena Manzo</i>	398
Giovan Battista Piranesi: the drawing of the vernacular in the representation of the solidity of the eighteenth century <i>Paolo Giordano</i>	403
Determining the Attitude-Behavior Gap Towards Sustainable Communities <i>Can Gölgecioglu, Simge Özdal Oktay</i>	408
Spolia Reconsidered in Terms of Sustainability <i>Hale Gönül</i>	417
Bell towers: Structural types and seismic safety <i>Mariateresa Guadagnuolo, Marianna Aurilio, Anna Tafuro, Giuseppe Faella</i>	423
Integrated approaches and strategies for enhancing sustainable development of Italian small villages in the South of Italy <i>Giuseppe Guida, Claudia de Biase, Fabiana Forte, Adriana Galderisi</i>	428
Accommodation strategies of Syrians in Turkey <i>Dilşa Günaydın Temel, Z. Ezgi Haliloğlu Kahraman</i>	433
Built environment heritage as political negotiation in Famagusta, Cyprus <i>Ceren Hamiloğlu</i>	439
Conceptual framework for developing next generation of Energy Performance Certification (EPC) systems <i>Timuçin Harputlugil</i>	443
Triconch chapels in the early Christian and Byzantine architectural tradition <i>Daniela Jacazzi</i>	449
Comparison of Design Criteria about Energy in Healthcare Building According to BREEAM and LEED Certification Systems <i>Sevil Jahed, Cüneyt Kurtay</i>	456
Sustaining Cultural Heritage Sites through Interpretation and Presentation Methods: The Case of Magnesia on the Meander <i>Başak Kalfa Ataklı, Nimet Özgönül</i>	463
Sustainability of Architectural Cultural Heritage in the Roman Imperial Period <i>Aygün Kalınbayrak Ercan</i>	469

Green Design; An Environmental Concern or An Aesthetic Approach <i>Aliye Raşan Karabetça</i>	474
Occupants' Behaviour for Sense of Security and Well Being Concerns in Their Residences: 100. Yıl Case <i>Özge Karaman</i>	479
Using Spolia in Ottoman Architecture: Searching for Continuity on an Architectural Symbol of Power through Re-use of Materials <i>Ceren Katipoğlu Özmen</i>	485
Analysis of Building Stock and Development of Building Typologies in Turkey <i>N. Cihan Kayaçetin, Gülsu Ulukavak Harputlugil, A. M. Husaunndee, M. S. Dizdaroğlu</i>	489
From Design to construction in Architecture A critical phase that redefines the role of the architect in the profession <i>Karen Boujaoudeh Khoury</i>	496
The room acoustic analysis of TED high school main lecture hall <i>Kivanc Kitapci</i>	502
Application of a multiple regression model for estimating the performance of a prismatic panel in varying room and window sizes <i>Büşra Köse, Tuğçe Kazanasmaz</i>	510
Hybrid biomimetic design for sustainable development through multiple perspectives <i>Carla Langella, Valentina Perricone</i>	515
Fashion eco design lab: capsule collections bio <i>Roberto Liberti, Patrizia Ranzo</i>	520
Historical thermal baths in Europe: a research methodology for restoration and preservation <i>Elena Manzo, Ilaria Pontillo</i>	525
The design from autarky to the circular economy <i>Angela Pecorario Martucci</i>	529
Medical retrofitting design <i>Sabina Martusciello, Massimiliano Masullo, Geremia Nappo, Alessandro Tessitore, Rosa De Micco, Antonio De Mase, Antonio Garofalo, Antonio Cennamo</i>	534
Wayfinding as an Aspect of Social Sustainability <i>İpek Memikoğlu, Hetham F. Layas</i>	538
Achieving Socially Sustainable Environments through Empathic Modelling <i>İpek Memikoğlu</i>	543
How can we make sustainable design? <i>Maria Dolores Morelli</i>	548

Design Strategies for Natural Ventilation <i>Francesca Muzzillo</i>	553
Blockchain technology: opportunities for sustainability of construction sector <i>Nadia Netti, Monica Cannaviello</i>	558
The actuality of MAT-Building or the deployed hub in the suburban contemporary territory <i>Gaspere Oliva</i>	563
Business continuity of lodging industry in the face of disasters: A case study from Turkey <i>Ezgi Orhan</i>	572
Sustainability of Heritage Conservation Council System in Turkey <i>Mustafa Önge</i>	576
Vernacular Techniques as Key to Sustainable Vernacular Architecture: The Case of Wattle and Daub Construction in Mediterranean Region <i>Hilal Tuğba Örmecioglu</i>	581
A step towards understanding industrial hemp: From hidden industry to a material in architecture <i>Esen Gökçe Özdamar</i>	587
Eco-industrial Parks and Sustainability: A Case of Green Organized Industrial Zone from Turkey <i>Suna S. Özdemir</i>	593
Environmental Problems and Policy in Australia <i>H. Nur Özkan Öztürk</i>	600
Defining Cittaslow requirements in the context of sustainability <i>Ayça Özmen</i>	605
Creating a start point for continuity of new educational approach by using design <i>Ahsen Öztürk</i>	612
Prediction of heat cost indicator in a home office using artificial neural network and genetic algorithm models <i>Yasemin Öztürk, Tuğçe Kazanasmaz, Gökmen Tayfur</i>	617
Comparison of material alternatives in a classroom in terms of daylight distribution and visual comfort survey <i>Yasemin Öztürk, Tuğçe Kazanasmaz, Arzu Cilasun Kunduracı</i>	623
“Reconstructing” Traditional Settlements in Cappadocia: Questions of Sustainability <i>Fatma Gül Öztürk Büke</i>	629
Sustainable Architectural Rehabilitation: the Palm tree Manor in Portugal <i>Ana Paula Pinheiro</i>	634

Energy, environmental and economic performance of an innovative solar heating network serving a small-scale Italian district <i>Antonio Rosato, Antonio Ciervo, Giovanni Ciampi, Michelangelo Scorpio, Sergio Sibilio, Luigi Maffei</i>	640
Sustainable Innovation: Design and New Technologies <i>Valentina Sapio</i>	648
The Change of Cultural Memory on an Iconic Historic Structure: Narmanlı Han <i>Sedef Sav</i>	652
The value of the scrap objects in design: which actions to promote it? <i>Francesca La Rocca, Chiara Scarpitti</i>	660
Suggestions for Refurbishment of Existing K-12 Schools in The Light of Sustainable Criteria <i>Hafize Nur Silay Emir</i>	668
Opaque and transparent innovative systems for a smart second skin building envelope <i>Sergio Sibilio, Antonio Rosato, Michelangelo Scorpio, Giovanni Ciampi, Giuseppina Iuliano, Yorgos Spanodimitriou</i>	678
Sustainable Urban Planning: Analysis of Open Public Spaces in Post-Soviet Districts of Lithuanian Cities <i>Jolita Sinkienė, Kęstutis Zaleckis, Indrė Gražulevičiūtė-Vileniškė, Jurga Vitkuvienė, Brigita Tranavičiūtė, Huriye Armağan Doğan, Tomas Grunskis</i>	686
An analysis on mixed-use high-rise residential complexes in Istanbul as to their prioritization of evaluation categories in LEED <i>Özge Süzer, Meltem Yılmaz</i>	690
A Conservation Process of Cultural Heritage: Ankara Saraçoğlu Quarter <i>Gülşah Şenocak</i>	698
Learning from Cohousing: Social Contact Design Patterns for Cohesion and Sustainability <i>Şule Taşlı Pektaş</i>	703
Urban transformation in Turkey; which aims disaster preventive and sustainable development or else? <i>Binali Tercan</i>	707
The sound as factor of reuse of Cultural Heritage in a modern key <i>Roxana Adina Toma, Massimiliano Masullo, Luigi Maffei</i>	710
Urban Conservation in Ankara is Sustainable ? Implementations in Ulus and Hacı Bayram Mosque Environs Since 30 Years <i>Mehmet Tunçer</i>	715
Sustainable Conservation of Cultural Landscape and Changing Values Around Hacıbayram Mosque and Augustus Temple <i>Mehmet Tunçer, Öznur Aytekin</i>	721

Evaluation of environmental factors in office environments with green intent in terms of user satisfaction: indoor air quality <i>Çetin Tünger, Zeynep Öktem, Ayça Turgay</i>	728
Environmental sustainability of being the leading building producer in Europe: developing valuable agricultural land for building construction in Turkey <i>Ali Türel</i>	735
The Social Role of Architectural Types: Cultural Sustainability in Architecture and the Possibility of Convention <i>Zeynep Çiğdem Uysal Ürey</i>	742
User Perception and Orientation in the Museum Designed by Re-Functioning: Erimtan Archeology and Art Museum Example <i>Şükran Büşra Ümütlü</i>	747
Collaborative and participative actions in design practices <i>Rosanna Veneziano</i>	751
Crisis of creative class: Hamburg and Naples right to the creative city <i>Federica Vingelli, Giuseppe Guida</i>	755
A bio-based grown material for living buildings <i>Antonella Violano, Salvatore Del Prete</i>	762
Ideology of Sustainable Architecture: A Critique <i>Onur Lami Yalman</i>	769
Sustainability of Rural Identity: Learning from Kıyıkışlacık's Self-Generated Experience <i>Damla Yeşilbağ</i>	773
Use-share service cases from Turkey: The impact of cultural traits <i>Can Uçkan Yüksel, Cigdem Kaya Pazarbasi</i>	780
Social & cultural sustainability: street art in Naples <i>Ornella Zerlenga</i>	785
WORKSHOPS	791
Workshop 1. Academic Research Design in Planning Studies: Migration and Sustainable Communities	792
Workshop 2. Building Performance Simulation: How Useful is It?	793
Workshop 3. Future Search Conference	794
Workshop 4. Resilient Building Design	795
Workshop 5. Sustainability and Resilience: how do we relate these concepts in planning debate and practices?	796
Workshop 6. Multisensorial Perception and Cultural Heritage Sites	797
Workshop 7. Urban art as Social & Cultural Sustainability	798
Workshop 8. Building with Earth	799

SUPPORTING ORGANIZATIONS	801
GRID “Architecture, Planning and Design Journal”	802
SID “Società Italiana Design”,	803
SITdA “Società Italiana della Tecnologia dell'Architettura”	804
LeNS “The Learning Network On Sustainability”; A New “Design Hope”: The Open And Distributed Lens, The Learning Network On Sustainability <i>Carlo Vezzoli, Cenk Basbolat</i>	805
INDEX	811

KEYNOTE SPEAKERS

Prof. Dr. Susan ROAF

Sue Roaf (B.A.Hons, A.A. Dipl., PhD, ARB, FRIAS) is Heriot Watt University's Emeritus Professor of Architectural Engineering and currently sits on the UK Architects Registration Board. An award winning architect, author and teacher she believes many modern buildings are very poorly designed for their climates and the only truly sustainable buildings are those run largely with natural energy. Subjects covered in her books include Ecohouse design. Adapting Buildings and Cities for Climate Change and Adaptive Thermal Comfort. She was Chair of the Passive Low Energy Architecture conference (www.plea2017.net) and is Co-Chair of the Windsor 2018 Conference on Comfort (www.windsorconference.com).

Prof. Dr. Birol KILKIŞ

Dr. Kilkis received his Ph.D. degree in Mechanical Engineering with high honors from Middle East Technical University. He graduated in 1972 with an honors degree from von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics in Belgium. He is a founder member of the Turkish Wind Energy Association, Turkish Solar Energy Association, and the past Country Coordinator of Wind Energy for CENTO. He taught graduate and undergraduate courses at several universities like Gannon University (full time), University of Missouri Rolla (adjunct) and Middle East Technical University (full time) since 1972. Currently, he is the head of Energy Engineering Graduate Program and a full-time professor at Baskent University. In total, he has published more than 500 papers in several journals and proceedings on a large variety of topics, and has several patents pending on green buildings, solar trigeneration, heat pump coupled cogeneration, and low-exergy HVAC systems. He is the North America Liaison of the Low-Exergy Buildings International Network and the founder of Exergy Analysis for Sustainable Buildings Technical Committee in ASHRAE.

Adaptive reuse in sustainable development: the case study of Ercolano (Italy)

Francesca Ciampa¹, Martina Bosone²

¹*Department of Architecture, University of Naples "Federico II", Naples, Italy,
francesca.c.16@hotmail.it*

²*Department of Architecture, University of Naples "Federico II", Naples, Italy,
martina.bosone@gmail.com*

Abstract: The research develops in the context of processes of sustainable adaptive reuse on urban scale. The document proposes a participatory methodological approach that, integrating interviews with privileged interlocutors and performance analysis of settlement processes, is used as an investigative tool in the phase of knowledge of the reuse project. The outcome is embodied in the elaboration of a vulnerability matrix that integrates the needs of the social system with the limits of transformability of the settlement system. This approach was used in the case study of Via Pugliano in Ercolano (Italy), characterized by the second hand economy linked to processes of re-use of fabrics. In this case, the adoption of multi-actors participatory process determined the identification of a framework of shared needs based on which it was possible to construct alternative scenarios of sustainable adaptive reuse. The goal integrates the physical, social and economic values expressed by local community.

Keywords: vulnerability matrix; sustainable adaptive reuse.

Introduction

Many cities on international level are experimenting with innovative processes, on a shared basis, for the regeneration of urban spaces. These practices act on built heritage incorporating the needs of the community (Council of Europe, 2005) and of the actors involved in the transformation processes of contexts. In the design phases, the enhancement of existing building resources is necessary to safeguard both physical and cultural values. In this perspective, the reuse project represents a strategic action to promote the extension of life cycle of settlement systems. In fact, it allows defining interventions that satisfy the new needs of users and integrate the physical, economic and social values expressed by the manufactured products and their contexts. The designing process of a sustainable recovery of settlements (Caterina, 2016) includes of new functions that give a second life to the degraded and abandoned building. In this perspective, the degraded and abandoned buildings are considered as an opportunity for experimentation and a potential for the development of settlement systems.

The object of the research is participatory methodological approach as an analytical tool in the phase of knowledge of the reuse project. This approach lets to elaborate design line

guides that integrate the needs of the community (ICOMOS, 2017) and the actors involved in the transformation processes of the contexts (Fiore, 2013).

The case study is via Pugliano, a street located in the modern city of Ercolano, near Naples. It needs to develop a sustainable reuse project because of the presence of a severely degraded physical system, subject to spontaneous transformation processes by the local community, and thus becoming vulnerable.

Methods

The creation of new synergies for the recovery of the physical system becomes an opportunity to recast the ability to preserve specific identities by building new values, relating the quality of the built environment with the productivity and innovation of local communities. Experimentation activates a process of social innovation that involves different actors in all phases of the planning process.

The research methodology is based on the hypothesis of an operative model for the knowledge, planning and management of urban productive contexts. This type of experimentation proposes a sustainable and operational model elaborated for its replicability. It consists of five main phases (fig. 1).

The first phase concerns the definition of a model of knowledge of the historical urban landscape (UNESCO, 2011). This phase highlights performance over time to identify the pressures and agents that have driven transformations on a local scale and on shared identification values. This phase involves a multilevel knowledge system on different scales: from the building to the urban aggregate, from the municipal to the intercommunal, combining expert knowledge with local knowledge in a multi-sectoral perspective.

The second phase starts with the interviews with privileged interlocutors to elaborate a complex knowledge model framework based on needs and expectances of different stakeholders. First, the Regions will be interested in investing in the cultural heritage of settlement systems. The second is the Municipalities, which will have the aim of revitalizing the economic and social systems of the city through an urban regeneration project. The third is the University, which will play the role of technical consultant to manage the quality of the project and will increase communication and collaboration between institution and local stakeholders. The fourth is the local community, which will be interested in improving living conditions both through maintenance/recovery action on built environment and through the

valorisation of local identity and culture. The last are the traders, which will reactivate the local economy.

The third phase includes the aim of this methodological approach that, regards the identification of a framework of shared needs, construct alternative scenarios of sustainable adaptive reuse. From the comparison among the needs expressed from different stakeholders and the analysis of performances offered by the settlement it is possible to deduce what it is possible to deduce what are the limits set by the examined contest to suffer further transformation processes. This phase defines the new changes that depend on the ability of the community to manage urban spaces or to build new relationships between physical and production processes. The level of quality depends on the correspondence between the user's needs and the framework question.

The fourth phase is the elaboration of a vulnerability matrix as outcome of the previous analytical phase (fig. 2). This matrix integrates the needs of the social system with the limits of transformability of the settlement system. The matrix, of a replicable nature depending on the case, deals with the themes of social, technological and urban planning at the same time. Broader frameworks, relating the different units of the environmental built (space) system with the social dynamics of the site, define the work. The matrix analyses the different spatial elements based on the processes in progress, intervention processes and caused phenomena, obtained through the perception of the community in the participated project actions. The drafting of an interpretative matrix of the different aspects of knowledge allows the harmonious coexistence between the "identity" recognized for this sector. In this way is possible to protect the identity of the asset in relation to the settlement system, ensuring a significant growth of economic and social values.

The last phase coincides with the elaboration of an urban-scale adaptive and inclusive reuse project that, basing on multi actor participatory approach, is able to protects the identity of the settlement system, guaranteeing a significant growth of the site's economic, cultural and social values.

Figure 1. Sustainable and operational model for adaptive reuse in sustainable development: the case study of Ercolano (Italy) (Ciampa, Bosone).

Findings and Discussion

The result of the research is a replicable operating model in different contexts. The sustainable and resilient regeneration (Walker et al., 2004; Folke et al., 2010, Resilience Alliance, 2010) of cultural heritage is based on actions of adaptive reuse of urban aggregates with a productive vocation. The fundamental principles derive from the application of a matrix of vulnerability to the context in which it operates. The proposed approach is based on the idea of rethinking the public space as a place influenced by the population in every phase of its life, not only in its use but also in its design. The collaboration among different stakeholders guides the strategies to elaborate a shared regenerative project. The basic process

is influenced by the role of an active community, which builds and controls the actions of regeneration. This vision manages the cultural values produced over time (Cerreta and De Toro, 2010). The innovativeness of the model developed consists in the role of the new local communities on the interaction between decision makers, stakeholders, users and designers. In this perspective the design process is sustainable because every decision is the result of the comparison and the consultation among different stakeholders and is directly connected with the needs and the expectances expressed by local community.

SOCIAL SYSTEM	SPACE SYSTEM	PROCESSES IN PROGRESS
Regions	space element: <i>Market Texile Place</i>	perceived physical degradation
Municipalities		unawareness of the potentiality of the site
University	space element: <i>Via Pugliano</i>	denial of the place's identity
		denial of the place's values
Traders	space element: <i>Ercolano</i>	failure to share civil values
		loss of cultural values and attractiveness of the site
Local Community	space element: <i>Ercolano</i>	absence of economic investments
		wrong interventions on the existing heritage
		economic suffering and increased crime
		emigration of the population from the site

Figure 2. Methodological vulnerability matrix for adaptive reuse in sustainable development: the case study of Ercolano (Italy) (Ciampa, Bosone).

Conclusion

The new sustainable landscape policy has to provide for constant recovery and maintenance actions as a means of productivity (Pinto and Viola, 2016). As recommended by the UNESCO Recommendations Recovery and Maintenance Strategies for the Historic Urban Landscape, the aim to protect the identity of the territories is the active role of local communities in landscape management. Many decision makers participate in maintenance, recovery, re-use and redevelopment of the landscape. Stakeholders allow local authorities to enable, together with the populations, a sustainable circle of research and training for the management of the territory.

References

- Caterina, G., (2016). Innovative strategies for the recovery of historic cities. *Techne*. (No. 12, pp. 33-35)
- Cerreta, M., & De Toro, P. (2010). Integrated Spatial Assessment for a Creative Decision-making Process: a Combined Methodological Approach to Strategic Environmental Assessment. *International Journal of Sustainable Development* (vol. 13, No. 1 / 2, pp. 17-30). Napoli.
- Council of Europe, (2005). Framework convention on the value of cultural heritage for society (Faro Convention). Web at: <http://conventions.coe.int>
- Fiore, V. (2013). Technological potential / figurative potential: reading for the control of urban transformations. In *Regenerating the cities of the Mediterranean*. LetteraVentidue. Siracusa.
- Carpenter S.R., Chapin T., Folke, C., Rockstrom J., Scheffer M., & Walker B. (2010). Resilience Thinking: Integrating Resilience, Adaptability and Transformability. In *Ecology and Society*. (vol. 15, No 4, pp. 20).
- ICOMOS. (2017). Delhi Declaration on Cultural Heritage and Democracy. Web at : <http://icomosga2017.org/delhi-declaration>.
- Pinto, M.R., & Viola, S. (2016). Material culture and planning commitment to recovery: Living Lab in the Parco del Cilento. *Techne*. (No. 12, pp. 223-229).
- Resilience Alliance (2010). Assessing Resilience in Social-Ecological Systems: Workbook for Practitioners. Version 2.0.
- UNESCO (2011). Recommendation on the Historic Urban Landscape. *UNESCO World Heritage Center*, Resolution 36C / 23, Annex, Paris, France.
- Carpenter, S.R., Holling, C.S., Kinzig, A., & Walker, B. (2004). Resilience, adaptability and transformability in social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society*. (vol.9, No.2, pp 5).

INDEX

Akbay, Saadet	64	Cioffi, Gianluca	184
Akdemir, Furkan	43	Cirafici, Alessandra	190
Al-Hafith, Omar	50	Cirillo, Vincenzo	195
Altay Kaya, Deniz	55	Corlito, Valentina	298
Alves, Susana	59	Corniello, Luigi	201
Argenziano, Pasquale	91, 153	Costanzo, Francesco	207
Atakan, Gökçe	64	Cristallo, Vincenzo	215
Ataman, Cem	70, 76	Cusano, Concetta	148
Atmaca, İlker	81	Çankaya Topak, Sıla	226
Aurilio, Marianna	423	Çavdar, Rabia Çiğdem	232
Avella, Alessandra	91	Çelebi Yazıcıoğlu, N. Mine	236
Aydın, Özlem	99	Çelik Başok, Gülşah	247
Aydın, Dicle	142	Çevik, Aslihan	253
Aytekin, Öznur	721	Çoban, Gamze	260
Bal Koçyiğit, Filiz	105	D'Aprile, Marina	269
Barani, Abdelhamed	111	Daneshvar Rouyandozagh, Yousef	275
Barbaros Akay, Emine	118	De Biase, Claudia	282, 428
Baş Bütüner, Funda	220	De Martino, Raffaella	287
Bellucci, Roberta	161	De Mase, Antonio	534
Berrin, Ayşem	220	De Matteis, Gianfranco	148, 292, 298
Bingöl, Ebru	133	de Wilde, Pieter	50, 306
Boganini, Leonardo	372	Del Prete, Salvatore	762
Bosone, Martina	174	Del Prete, Antonino	292
Boussora, K.	390	Demir, Başak	310
Burak Bican, Nezh	123	di Vico, Barbara	287
Büken Cantimur, Burcu	137	Diñç Kalaycı, Pınar	260
Büyükşahin Sıramkaya, Süheyla	142	Dizdaroğlu, M. S.	489
Cacace, Daniela	148	Doğan, Huriye Armağan	315, 686
Campone, Carolina	153	Dokmeci Yorukoglu, Papatya Nur	331
Cannaviello, Monica	558	Duarte, Rui	319
Carillo, Saverio	153	Ekiz, Aslinur	43
Caruso, Ivo	215	Elmalı Şen, Derya	324
Carusone, Marco	161	Eshtiwı, Ehab Ali	331
Castanò, Francesca	167	Etyemez Çıplak, Leyla	336
Cennamo, Claudia	148	Faella, Giuseppe	423
Cennamo, Antonio	534	Fernanda María, Garcia Marino	384
Ciampa, Francesca	174	Fırat, Hasan Baran	344
Ciampi, Giovanni	640, 678	Fiorentino, Caterina	190
Cianfanelli, Elisabetta	180		
Ciervo, Antonio	640		

**BEYOND ALL LIMITS 2018: International Congress on Sustainability in Architecture,
Planning, and Design, 17-19 October 2018, Ankara, Turkey**

Fiorillo, Raffaella	349	Langella, Carla	515
Forte, Fabiana	428, 798	Layas, Hetham F.	538
Franchino, Rossella	356, 362	Liberti, Roberto	520
Frettoloso, Caterina	362, 367	Maffei, Luigi	344, 640, 710, 797
Galderisi, Adriana	428, 796	Maliqari, Andrea	201
Gallo, Paola	367, 372	Manzo, Elena	398, 525
Gambardella, Claudio	379	Martucci, Angela Pecorario	529
Garofalo, Antonio	534	Martusciello, Sabina	534
Ghida, Nassila	390	Masullo, Massimiliano	344, 534, 710
Gianetti, Anna	398	Memikoğlu, İpek	538, 543
Giordano, Paolo	403	Meydan Yıldız, Seçil Gül	81
Gölgelioğlu, Can	408	Mirra, Enrico	201
Gönül, Hale	417	Monaco, Michela	282
Grunskis, Tomas	686	Morelli, Maria Dolores	548
Guadagnuolo, Mariateresa	423	Mottola, Carla	201
Guida, Giuseppe	428, 755	Muzzillo, Francesca	553
Günaydın Temel, Dilşa	433	Nappo, Geremia	534
Gürsel Dino, İpek	70, 76	Netti, Nadia	558
Haliloğlu Kahraman, Z. Ezgi	433	Okyay, Gülce G.	137
Hamiloğlu, Ceren	439	Oliva, Gaspare	563
Harputlugil, Timuçin	443	Orhan, Ezgi	572
Husaunndee, A. M.	489	Öktem, Zeynep	728
İlgın Bahçeci, Hazal	81	Önge, Mustafa	576
Ippolito, Fabrizia	190	Örmecioğlu, Hilal Tuğba	118, 581
Iuliano, Giuseppina	678	Özdal Oktay, Simge	408
Jacazzi, Danila	449	Özdamar, Esen Gökçe	587
Jahed, Sevil	456	Özdemir, Suna S.	593
Kahraman, Zerrin Ezgi	111	Özgönül, Nimet	463
Kalfa Ataklı, Başak	463	Özkan Öztürk, H. Nur	600
Kalınbayrak Ercan, Aygün	469	Özmen, Ayça	605, 799
Karabetça, Aliye Rahşan	474	Öztürk, Ahsen	612
Karaman, Özge	479	Öztürk, Yasemin	617, 623
Katipoğlu Özmen, Ceren	485	Öztürk, Elif	324
Kaya Pazarbasi, Cigdem	780	Öztürk Büke, Fatma Gül	629
Kayaçetin, N. Cihan	489	Perricone, Valentina	515
Kazanasmaz, Tuğçe	253, 510, 617, 623	Pinheiro, Ana Paula	634
Khoury, Karen Boujaoudeh	496	Pisacane, Nicola	91, 362
Kıraç, A. Binnur	137	Pontillo, Ilaria	525
Kitapci, Kivanc	502	Ranzo, Patrizia	520
Köse, Büşra	510	Rosa De Micco, Rosa	534
Kumkale Acikgoz, Ece	275	Rosato, Antonio	640, 678
Kurtay, Cüneyt	456	Russo, Michela	161
La Rocca, Francesca	660	Russo, Dario	379

**BEYOND ALL LIMITS 2018: International Congress on Sustainability in Architecture,
Planning, and Design, 17-19 October 2018, Ankara, Turkey**

Sapio, Valentina	648	Zerlenga, Ornella	785, 798
Satish , B. K.	50	Zizi, Mattia	292
Sav, Sedef	652		
Sbordone, Maria Antonietta	282		
Scarpitti, Chiara	660		
Scorpio, Michelangelo	640, 678		
Silay Emir, Hafize Nur	668		
Sibilio, Sergio	640, 678		
Sinkienè, Jolita	686		
Soleti, Graziella	298		
Spanodimitriou, Yorgos	678		
Stasi, Renato	180		
Süzer, Özge	690		
Şekerci, Yaren	118		
Şenocak, Gülşah	698		
Tafuro, Anna	423		
Taşlı Pektaş, Şule	703		
Tercan, Binali	707		
Tessitore, Alessandro	534		
Toma, Roxana Adina	710		
Tranavičiūtė, Brigita	686		
Tufarelli, Margherita	180		
Tunçer, Mehmet	715, 721		
Tünger, Çetin	728		
Türel, Ali	735		
Ulukavak Harputlugil, Gülsu	489, 793		
Ulvi, Hayri	43		
Uysal Ürey, Zeynep Çiğdem	742		
Ümütlü, Şükran Büşra	747		
Veneziano, Rosanna	751		
Vingelli, Federica	755		
Viola, Serena	356		
Violano, Antonella	762, 794		
Vitkuvienė, Jurga	686		
Yaldız, Esra	142		
Yalman, Onur Lami	769		
Yeşilbağ, Damla	773		
Yetim, Evşen	324		
Yıldırım, Nazlı Nazende	105		
Yılmaz, Meltem	690		
Yılmaz, Saime	43		
Yüksel, Can Uçkan	780		
Zaleckis, Kęstutis	686		

**BEYOND
ALL
LIMITS
CONGRESS
2018**

<https://beyondallimits.cankaya.edu.tr>

Supporting Organizations:

SID Società Italiana di Design
Italian Design Society
identità culturale e scientifica del design italiano
scientific and cultural identity of Italian design

SITdA
Società Italiana della Tecnologia dell'Architettura

LENS
the Learning Network
on Sustainability

ISBN: 978-975-6734-20-9